

Appendix S7. Estimates of broad sense heritability using frequentist and Bayesian approaches.

Table S3: Estimates of broad sense heritability (H^2) using either frequentist (*glmmTMB*) or Bayesian (*MCMCglmm*) statistical approaches. 95% confidence intervals are provided for each estimate except for non-Gaussian traits under the frequentist approach. Non-gaussian traits report estimates on the latent scale.

Trait	<i>glmmTMB</i> / <i>lme4</i> Family	Field H^2 (95% C.I)	G.H H^2 (95% C.I)	<i>MCMCglmm</i> Family	Field H^2 (95% C.I)	G.H H^2 (95% C.I)
Leaf number	Gaussian	0.075 (0.046, 0.11)	0.085 (0.040, 0.13)	Gaussian	0.080 (0.043, 0.12)	0.088 (0.031, 0.15)
Height	Gaussian	0.086 (0.054, 0.12)	0.13 (0.078, 0.19)	Gaussian	0.091 (0.051, 0.14)	0.14 (0.062, 0.21)
Inflorescences	Poisson	0.19 (no CI)	0.13 (no CI)	Poisson	0.27 (0.11, 0.44)	0.83 (0.48, 0.99)
Siliques	Zero-inflated negative binomial	3.39e-4 (no CI)	2.67e-6 (no CI)	Poisson	0.065 (0.030, 0.11)	0.062 (5.19e-7, 0.12)